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HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D3.4

Pilot region 4- Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras (PT) report

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D3.4
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Pilot region 4-Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras (PT) report
WORK PACKAGE	WP3
DELIVERABLE TYPE	R
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	P
DUE DATE	31.10.2025 (Month 34)
PAGES	67
DOCUMENT VERSION	3.0
LEAD AUTHOR(S)	Susana Serôdio (APREN)
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The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	25.07.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Chrisitian Mikovits, Eva Maria Konrad (BOKU)	Creation
0.2	08.10.2025	Susana Serôdio, Diogo Carvalheda, Mariana Carvalho (APREN), Thomas Schauppenlehner (BOKU)	Consolidation of input from contributors
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	20.10.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Eva Maria Schöll, Karl Bittner, Eva Maria Konrad (BOKU), Claudio Moscoloni, Giuseppe Giorgi (PoliTO)	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	30.10.2025	Susana Serôdio, Diogo Carvalheda, Mariana Carvalho (APREN)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
2.0	30.10.2025	Luis Ramirez Camargo (UU)	Coordinator review
2.1	31.10.2025	Name, Organisation (short name)	Consolidation of input from coordinator
2.2	31.10.2025	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator approval
FINAL VERSION			
3.0	31.10.2025	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract This report presents the WIMBY project activities conducted in the Portuguese pilot site regions of Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras, focusing on social perceptions and acceptance of wind energy and repowering projects. Using immersive 3D workshops, Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MUSA), mental model mapping and semi-structured interviews, the study engaged 53 stakeholders with diverse backgrounds. Results show that Portugal's mature wind fleet and grid constraints make repowering a key pathway to meet 2030 targets. The immersive 3D planning tool proved highly effective in visualising spatial scenarios and has strong potential to support permitting processes by enhancing communication and transparency. Overall, participants expressed positive attitudes towards wind energy, while visual and proximity impacts remain key concerns, particularly in Torres Vedras.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
iSIP	Sistema de Identificação Parcelar
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Aiding
MUSA	Multicriteria Satisfaction Analysis
nDSM	Normalized Digital Surface Model
NEWA	New European Wind atlas
OSM	Open Street Map
SPSS	Statistical Product and Service Solutions
VR	Virtual Reality
WCMC	World Conservation Monitoring Centre

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the methods and results of the activities conducted in the Portuguese pilot site regions of Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras within the WIMBY project. The work aimed to explore social perceptions and acceptance of wind energy and specifically repowering projects in a country where the wind fleet is already mature, and many wind turbines will reach the end of their operational lifetime by 2030. In this context, the study tested participatory and visualisation tools for enhancing communication and transparency in the permitting process, while assessing stakeholder preferences regarding different repowering configurations and identifying the main drivers of acceptance.

The activities in Portugal were carried out under the coordination of APREN, with the support of BOKU University. APREN organised and led the workshops, ensured local stakeholder engagement, and provided the data and contextual information that supported much of the analysis. Several other WIMBY partners – KIE, UU, PSI, DBL, and NAZKA – contributed to the design and implementation of the participatory methods and subsequent analyses.

In total, seven workshops were held across both pilot regions, involving over fifty participants from public authorities, developers, grid operators, academia, and civil society.

The Portuguese pilot site activities demonstrated the potential of interactive and participatory tools to foster informed discussions on wind energy planning and repowering. The immersive 3D workshops enabled participants to visualise spatial scenarios, explore trade-offs, and engage in dialogue about feasible repowering strategies. In general, repowering was perceived as an efficient and less environmentally intrusive option than greenfield development, although landscape aesthetics and proximity to residential areas remained sensitive topics, particularly in Torres Vedras. Therefore, many participants favoured layouts with a higher number of smaller turbines (around 4 MW) rather than fewer larger ones (6 MW), especially nearby populated areas.

The complementary MUSA survey confirmed broadly positive attitudes towards wind energy, with respondents recognising its role in

decarbonisation and regional development while maintaining expectations regarding environmental assessments and mitigation measures. The mental model mapping exercise revealed strong awareness of the links between renewable energy, CO₂ reduction, and climate change, alongside concerns about biodiversity and noise emissions. Semi-structured interviews further indicated that local acceptance can be strengthened through early engagement, transparent communication, and financial participation mechanisms.

Overall, the Portuguese pilot site activities achieved its main objectives, successfully generating quantitative and qualitative insights into stakeholder perceptions and acceptance factors in two distinct regional contexts. The only minor deviation concerned the absence of workshops with school and students, due to scheduling limitations during the academic period, as well as a lower participation of university students given that the workshops coincided with the exam season.

The results provide valuable feedback on the effectiveness of the immersive 3D platform (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024), contribute to the comparative analysis of satisfaction indices in Deliverable 4.6 (in progress), and complement the stakeholder mapping methodologies presented in Deliverable 4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024). More broadly, the Portuguese experience confirms that interactive visualisation and participatory tools can play a decisive role in supporting future permitting and spatial planning processes for wind energy and repowering projects. By making complex information accessible and tangible, these tools can help build trust, strengthen dialogue between authorities, developers, and communities, and promote a more inclusive approach to renewable energy deployment, which is a crucial step towards achieving Portugal's 2030 renewable energy targets.

Note to readers: This report is part of a series of four pilot studies conducted as part of the WIMBY project. Each report focuses on the respective regional results. However, to ensure the readability of each individual report, there is some minor overlap in content (e.g. process descriptions, methods).

1 Introduction

1.1 Case Study Description

Portugal is a privileged country in what regards its geographical location, which contributes to extremely favourable weather conditions to produce electricity from various renewable sources. Considering data from the Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG, 2025), the country currently relies on more than 70% of renewable electricity and, despite the dependence on conventional energy sources, is actively pursuing sustainable energy initiatives to reduce carbon emissions and increase renewable energy adoption, with an ambitious target of 93% of renewable incorporation until 2030 (Portuguese Government - Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2024). Wind energy plays a significant role, which, according to the proposed targets, will increase in the coming years, mostly by repowering existing projects.

According to DGEG (2025), Portugal currently has 5.9 GW of installed wind power capacity, which, in 2024, covered 26% of the electricity demand (REN, 2025). The Portuguese National and Energy Climate Plan for 2030 (Portuguese Government - Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2024) sets new capacity targets for wind, aiming to reach a total of 10.4 GW of onshore wind and 2.0 GW of offshore wind by 2030. To reach the onshore wind target, Portugal not only needs to develop new facilities, but above all repower existing projects, as half of the wind turbines currently in operation reach their end of life by 2030 (APREN, 2025).

Figure 1: Number of wind turbines per age by the end of 2024. Sources: Yearbook APREN 2025; APREN analysis

The Portuguese wind fleet is relatively mature, as illustrated by the high number of turbines aged between 15 and 20 years (see Figure 1). According to APREN’s members, the average operational lifetime of wind turbines in Portugal is estimated to be around 20 to 25 years (APREN, 2020). This indicates that a considerable portion of the installed capacity will soon reach the end of its operational lifetime, highlighting the importance of efficient repowering strategies.

Figure 2: Evolution of installed capacity in the Portuguese electricity generation system.
Sources: REN; DGE; NEPC 2030 review; APREN analysis

The feasibility of these expansion plans is highly dependent on the communication and cooperation between stakeholders, grid operators, authorities and local communities, to ensure low environmental impact and public and community support.

APREN – The Portuguese Renewable Energy Association was the local partner of the WIMBY Project, being responsible for managing the pilot regions, organising open days and workshops, and ensuring the communication with different stakeholders. APREN is a non-profit association founded in October 1988. Its mission is to coordinate and represent the common interests of its members, promoting renewables energies in the electricity field. APREN works together with official bodies and other similar entities, at national and international levels, constituting an instrument of participation in energy and environmental policies through the use and valorisation of natural resources for electricity production, namely in the fields of hydro, wind, solar, geothermal, biomass, biogas and urban solid waste.

With the goals of the WIMBY project in mind, and the fact the wind technology is quite mature in the country, APREN chose two Portuguese municipalities as pilot sites: Viana do Castelo (North, see Figure 3) and Torres Vedras (Centre, see Figure 4). Both areas are already familiar with wind energy and welcomed a very interesting number of wind farms throughout the years. Those municipalities will soon face the challenge of repowering to meet the 2030 NECP targets. Despite this, they do have different approaches and perceptions regarding renewable energy, specifically wind power.

Viana do Castelo (Figure 3) is a hub for renewable energy projects, particularly for offshore and onshore wind energy. Onshore projects have been present since 2005. The municipality has gained recognition for hosting innovative key initiatives, such as the industrial facilities for the manufacturing of blades and rotors of turbines, but also the WindFloat project, which positions it as a leader in sustainable energy solutions and a key player in advancing Portugal's green energy transition.

Additionally, Viana do Castelo contains areas with significant wind potential, reinforcing its role as a key player in renewable energy innovation. The strong contribution of renewable energy – particularly wind – to the local communities through job creation and regional investment has also played a key role in fostering local acceptance of wind energy projects.

On the other hand, Torres Vedras (Figure 4), a municipality from the Portuguese centre west region, often called the "land of wind", is one of the Portuguese municipalities with several wind farms installed, which cover around 98% of the municipality's electricity production (Câmara Municipal de Torres Vedras, 2022).

The high presence of this technology, combined with its proximity to residential areas, the fact that some wind farms are located within the National Ecological Reserve, and close many tourist places of the Portuguese coastline, makes local acceptance less favourable and not entirely unanimous. Even so, this context makes the region an excellent pilot site for the WIMBY project to test and enhance engagement and communication with the various local stakeholders.

Figure 3: Overview of the Viana do Castelo pilot region and its location in Portugal (Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Municípa, S.A.); Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Figure 4: Overview of the Torres Vedras pilot region and its location in Portugal (Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Municípa, S.A.); Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Both regions have wind power plants in operation. By the end of 2024, the total onshore wind installed capacity in the municipality of Torres Vedras was 94 MW, out of a total of 314 MW in the Lisbon district. In contrast, the municipality of Viana do Castelo had a lower installed capacity of 37 MW, although it is part of a district with a higher total capacity of 429 MW.

For the immersive 3D planning game, an assumed target was set for each region, derived from the national target for 2030 and based on their current installed capacity. Given the current bottlenecks in connecting new projects, due to limited grid availability, the main purpose of the immersive 3D planning game was to evaluate whether participants would prefer to reduce

the number of wind turbines through repowering (i.e., replacing old, smaller turbines with fewer, larger ones) or adopt other approaches involving the installation of new projects.

1.2 Objective

Viana do Castelo aims to build on its leadership in renewable energy innovation, supported by offshore and onshore projects, industrial infrastructure, and strong community acceptance. With significant wind potential and a key role in the national energy transition, the region is well positioned to explore future development pathways.

Torres Vedras, known as the “land of wind,” faces the challenge of balancing a high concentration of wind farms with local acceptance issues, due to proximity to residential areas, protected areas and touristic places. Its context makes it an ideal pilot site for testing new strategies to strengthen stakeholder engagement.

In both regions, the immersive 3D planning game aimed to explore whether participants would prefer repowering existing wind farms or alternative approaches involving the development of new wind energy projects, considering current grid limitations. Moreover, the objective was to assess public perception, social acceptance, and local priorities regarding the modernisation of older wind farms—some of which are approaching the end of their operational life—while also examining how repowering could minimise land use impacts, optimise existing infrastructure, and accelerate renewable energy deployment without the need for new spatial planning procedures.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Participant engagement

The stakeholder engagement strategy for the workshops held in Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras was coordinated by APREN, which took the lead in disseminating the initiative and issuing invitations. The initial step was to contact both municipalities directly and get them involved in the project.

To ensure a holistic and inclusive approach to wind farm repowering, which stands as a cornerstone of the WIMBY Project and the foundation for

successful wind development in Portugal, the selection of workshop participants was carefully designed to reflect the diversity of perspectives and expertise required to overcome main barriers to deploy a repowering project.

APREN proceeded to invite, via email and follow-up by phone, a broad range of stakeholders, including:

- Official entities involved in renewable energy project permitting procedure;
- Local town hall, parish councils and residents' associations;
- Local academic institutions (targeting both professors and students)
- Grid Operators
- Developers with projects in or near the selected regions;
- Nature conservation associations;
- National and regional authorities involved in permitting process;
- Other relevant stakeholders.

Based on the availability gathered through a preliminary survey, workshop slots were organised to ensure a heterogeneous mix of participants in each session, with different views that could produce richer insights. This diversity enriched the immersive game discussions by incorporating distinct perspectives and allowing both organizers and participants to learn from each other's expertise.

The decision to send invitations by email was based on APREN's experience in organising workshops with different stakeholders in various geographies of the country, with the confidence that it would be possible to secure enough participants to carry out the workshops.

APREN also did an effort to reach out to schools, not only on a university level but also elementary and high schools. Despite managing to have professors and university students in the workshops in both locations, it was not possible to visit a school and deploy a WIMBY class. This happened due to lack of availability of the schools and also the timing, which was a holiday / exam period for some institutions.

2.2 Locations

The initial goal was to host the workshops in public spaces such as libraries or community centres, in order to create a more inclusive and less formal

atmosphere. This type of setting was considered important to avoid the potentially intimidating feel of corporate venues and to help participants feel more at ease. While it was not possible to organise such a venue in Viana do Castelo due to lack of availability – the workshops were carried out in a hotel in city centre – Torres Vedras provided a more suitable setting, with the workshops being held at the city’s Environmental Education Centre.

2.3 Pilot site activities

The activities at the pilot sites include the following (see Figure 5):

- **Immersive 3D planning game:** an interactive scenario planning tool with immersive 3 D visualisation designed to engage people and promote discussion about trade-offs, fears and expectations regarding wind power development
- **MUSA Survey:** a structured survey to quantify how residents evaluate the entire range of wind farm impacts
- **Mental Models:** a method used to explore perceptions and understanding of the impacts of wind energy
- **Semi-structured interviews:** focused on project ramifications and acceptance
- **Other activities:** supplementary stakeholder engagement efforts aimed at collecting qualitative feedback on the interactive map, the general forum, and broader insights into the projects overall approach and methodology

Figure 5: Outline of activities for the pilot regions in Portugal (Graphic: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

The immersive 3D planning game was tailored to each specific pilot site and, together with the mental models, conducted during workshops with participants. Individuals were approached in public spaces, such as streets or local hotspots, for the MUSA Survey and the interviews on project impacts and acceptance. In some cases, interviews were also conducted with workshop participants after the sessions concluded. Other activities included a brief presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum, as well as semi-structured video interviews with selected stakeholders.

2.4 Immersive 3D Planning Game

2.4.1 Workshop Design and Data Collection

The planning game workshops aimed to explore potential wind energy developments and repowering strategies through an interactive experience using immersive 3D visualisations and a planning game approach. For this purpose, the BOKU team developed an immersive 3D platform comprising three interacting components (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Core components of the immersive 3D platform developed for the four pilot sites within the WIMBY project (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024)

Data processing utilised free, open-source, site-specific data (Table 1), which was enhanced through manual and semi-automatic optimisations and provided the foundation for the game board, the game logic and the development of immersive 3D environment.

The serious game approach relied on three types of visual output:

- The **game table output**, which served as a playing area for creating wind energy scenarios and working with maps during the workshops, using game bricks as input device;
- The **projector output**, to present a dashboard with 3D visuals, key data and environmental details; and
- The **immersive VR output**, which allowed users to explore realistic visualisations of their envisaged wind energy scenarios using VR glasses.

For more information on the immersive 3D platform, see Deliverable D5.3 (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024).

The workshops in the case study regions were divided into five stages:

1. **Welcoming and introduction**, including a briefing on the objectives and procedure of the workshop
2. **Baseline survey**
3. **Planning game and interaction with the 3D visualization**, where participants engaged with the platform
4. **Interactive discussions and summary of the workshop**, to reflect on outcomes and insights
5. **Debrief/feedback survey**

Data collection during the workshop focused on participant engagement, learning outcomes, and decision-making. A baseline survey (stage 2) assessed participants' knowledge, attitudes toward wind energy, and prior experience with participatory processes. A debrief and feedback survey at the end (stage 5) evaluated the 3D game's usability, learning impact, the immersive experience, and the overall process.

The immersive 3D planning game consists of two game phases, whereas game phase 1 addresses the identification of inclusion and exclusion zones and game phase 2 focuses on the virtually planning of windfarms to achieve given regional targets.

During the planning game, participants' statements, reasoning, questions, and concerns regarding game decisions were documented, with time stamps added to link them to specific game actions. Separate notes were also taken to record general observations of group dynamics and interactions during the game.

2.4.2 Geospatial data sources

The immersive 3D environment depends on high-resolution and up-to-date datasets for accurate and realistic visualisations. Table 1 below summarizes all datasets used and processed to build the visualisations and convey supplementary information.

The public availability of high-resolution data in Portugal is limited compared to other European countries. For instance, the required Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and a Digital Surface Model (DSM) of the target regions had to be acquired from proprietary providers to ensure accurate topographical and surface representation for simulation and visualisation purposes.

Moreover, also OpenStreetMap (OSM) data on infrastructure was obviously incomplete. Therefore, the dataset on buildings was a combination of Microsoft Global ML Building Footprints and OSM.

Table 1: Datasets used for creating the 3D environment and game logic for the Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras pilot region

Category	Dataset	Source	Licence	URI/Comment
Topography	Digital Surface Model (DSM)	Município S.A.	Restricted	N/A
	Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	Município S.A.	Restricted	N/A
	Normalized Digital Surface Model (nDSM)	Derivate of [DSM, DTM]	Restricted	Created for internal use only
Land Cover	Carta de Uso e Ocupação do Solo	Direção-Geral do Território	CC BY 4.0	https://dados.gov.pt/en/datasets/carta-de-uso-e-ocupacao-do-solo-cos-2018-rdf-projeto-cross-forest-land-use-land-cover-map-cos-2018-rdf-cross-forest-project/
	Sistema de Identificação Parcelar (Ísip)	Instituto de Financiamento da Agricultura e Pescas	CC BY 4.0	https://www.ifap.pt/isip/ows/
Infrastructure	Wind turbines	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Power lines	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Fences, Hedges, Walls	Derivate of [Roads, Buildings]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
	Extra Objects	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Building Footprints	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Global ML Building Footprints	Microsoft	ODbL	https://github.com/microsoft/GlobalMLBuildingFootprints
	Roads	OSM	ODbL	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway
	Energy	Wind Capacity Factor	New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International
Wind Speeds		New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://map.neweuropeawindatlas.eu
Potential for Wind Turbine Locations		Derivate of [DTM, Infrastructure, Wind Speeds]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Environmental data	World Database on Protected Areas (2024)	IUCN and UNEP-WCMC	Non-Commercial use	https://www.protectedplanet.net

2.5 Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MUSA) framework

To capture a nuanced picture of how wind farms are affecting or will affect local communities, we designed a comprehensive satisfaction framework that runs in parallel with the 3D planning game workshops. Its primary aim is to quantify how residents judge the full spectrum of wind-farm impacts, from noise, landscape change, and biodiversity concerns to local employment, community contribution. Because these dimensions often pull in different directions, analysing them one by one would hide critical trade-offs. Instead, we applied a multi-criteria setting that evaluates all aspects simultaneously.

The core of this setting is the Multicriteria Satisfaction Analysis (MUSA), a well-established method within the wider family of Multi-Criteria Decision Aiding (MCDA) (Grigoroudis & Siskos, 2002). MUSA was originally created for customer-satisfaction studies in the service sector. The approach relies on preference disaggregation: participants rate each criterion on a tailored Likert scale¹, and the algorithm infers criterion weights, partial value functions, and global satisfaction indices via ordinal regression. By deriving these parameters directly from response patterns, rather than asking analysts or respondents to assign weights manually, MUSA avoids the subjective bias common in many MCDA approaches.

As illustrated in Figure 7, MUSA deconstructs global satisfaction into criterion-level components, showing how each attribute contributes to the overall score. This hierarchical view highlights both strengths and areas needing improvement, providing a transparent roadmap for raising public acceptance. In practice, residents complete a survey that records both their overall satisfaction with nearby wind farms and their specific ratings on each criterion, using an ordered scale such as a five-point Likert range from “Extremely dissatisfied” to “Extremely satisfied.” This ordinal information will be entered into MUSA and converted into weighted scores.

¹ For example, “Undesired land-use changes” can use a four-point Likert scale with options “To a large extent”, “To a moderate extent”, “To a lesser extent”, “Not at all”. Whereas “Economic impact on the community” can use a five-point scale with options “Rather negative”, “Slightly negative”, “No effect”, “Slightly positive”, “Rather positive”.

Figure 7: Structure of a MUSA problem (Huang et al., 2024)

We embed MUSA in our broader Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MCSA) framework, which adds the practical guideline needed for field application (as shown in Figure 8). For detailed introduction of the MCSA framework, please refer to Deliverable D4.2 (Huang et al., 2024).

Figure 8: Satisfaction analysis workflow (Huang et al., 2024)

2.6 Mental Models

We investigated workshop participants' mental models of perceived wind energy impacts. Mental models explore individuals' cognitive representations of the external world, including perceptions of interrelations within a system and system components (Van Den Broek et al., 2025). To elicit these mental models, we apply a standardised mental model tool called M-Tool (Van Den Broek et al., 2021)², which allows participants to create their mental model by mapping relevant concepts, in our case, the perceived impacts of wind farms, and the directional relations as an influence diagram (Van Den Broek et al., 2021). We applied a two-step approach. In the first step, we compiled wind farm impacts from a literature review and from a survey with the target audience. In the survey participants were asked about the impacts of wind farms they could think of in all four pilot site countries to determine the most commonly perceived impacts. We analysed the open text responses where people described wind farm impacts following the guidelines on conducting thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2023). We applied a deductive or “theory-driven” approach, where produced codes are predefined through a theoretically informed interpretation by the researcher, in this case based on the impacts reported in relevant literature (Byrne, 2022). A selection of 20 impacts was made, comprising the most mentioned social, ecological, economic and energy production-related impacts (see Figure 9).

² <https://m-tool.org/>

Figure 9: Selection of impacts and the target variable (wind farm) used for the mental model exercise (Graphic: Leanda Vedder)

In the second step, participants could use these impacts to create their mental model by connecting them with each other or the target variable, the wind farm in operation, with three weighted arrows, where the weight represents the strength of the influence between images (see Figure 7). Participants were handed tablets with headphones where they were first presented with an instruction video that explained the concepts and instructions of how to create their model, then they were prompted to create their mental model about impacts they expect or have experienced from wind farms. Afterwards, they filled in a short survey on their general attitude towards wind farms (on a scale from 0 = I fully oppose wind farms, to 100 = I fully support wind farms), their perspective on the energy transition and renewable energy policies. We applied a network analysis approach to analyse the data, where the impacts serve as nodes and the arrows represent the edges of the network. In this way, we investigate the most used impacts, the most used direct connections between concepts and the most used indirect connections for each case study. This allows us to gain insights into participants' understanding of the system, especially the indirect connections, which provide us with an understanding of participants' capability to conceptualise complex interrelations and systems thinking.

Figure 10: M-Tool mapping screen with a mental model created by a participant.
(Graphic: Leanda Vedder).

The mental model exercise was implemented in conjunction with the 3D immersive environment during the workshops. To control for the potential influence of the 3D experience on participants' perceptions of wind farm impacts, efforts were made to achieve an even distribution of participants completing the mental model task either before or after engaging with the 3D environment. This allocation was determined based on the specific workshop arrangements in each pilot region. In Portugal, the mental model exercise was administered either before or after the 3D immersive experience on the same day of the workshops, which were organised into multiple sessions. For each workshop day, one group completed the mental model exercise prior to the 3D activity (N=21), while the other group did so afterwards (N=28). Additionally, one participant completed the mental model exercise without attending the workshop.

2.7 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

The term NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard) is widely used to describe local opposition to nearby developments, particularly those involving energy infrastructure such as wind turbines or transmission lines (Devine-Wright, 2009). As Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016) argue, negative externalities associated with wind energy projects (e.g., noise or visual intrusions) can foster NIMBYism. These localised externalities manifest in several ways. A

concise review of the literature identifies four primary drivers of local resistance: (i) the environmental impacts of wind energy projects; (ii) their technical and physical characteristics; (iii) the distribution of costs and benefits related to the project; and (iv) the behaviour and practices of project developers.

With respect to **environmental impacts**, research highlights several key concerns: noise emissions (Langer et al., 2016, 2017); perceived levels of infrasound (Langer et al., 2018); the visual prominence of wind turbines (Langer et al., 2016, 2017) and their setback distances (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016); shadow flicker (Devine-Wright, 2005; Jensen et al., 2014); impacts on biodiversity (Ladenburg & Dubgaard, 2009) and property values (Jensen et al., 2014); grid expansion associated with projects (Langer et al., 2018); and the broader regional distribution of turbines (Bidwell, 2013).

Regarding **physical characteristics**, studies primarily focus on turbine height and the number of turbines. Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016), using a discrete choice experiment, found that higher turbines require greater compensation payments to ensure local acceptance. They also observed that residents demand increased compensation for each additional turbine within a wind farm. Similarly, Langer et al. (2016) confirmed that the steady expansion of turbines in Bavaria, Germany, has intensified conflicts with local communities.

Research on the **distribution of costs and benefits** underscores the importance of perceived distributive justice (Ciupuliga & Cuppen, 2013; Huijts et al., 2012;). Community benefits and financial participation have been shown to positively influence local acceptance (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Research suggests that community benefits are better apt to increase wind energy project acceptance than individual benefits (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Walker et al., 2014; Walter, 2014). However, many studies also detected cheaper electricity for locals as convincing benefit (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Cass et al., 2010). It should be noted that some residents might perceive financial benefits as bribery (Cass et al., 2010; Macdonald et al., 2017).

Finally, the **behaviour of wind energy developers** plays a crucial role in acceptance. Studies highlight that perceived trustworthiness strongly influences public attitudes (Graham et al., 2009; Jobert et al., 2007). Trust

can be fostered by enhancing procedural justice, particularly through transparent and high-quality information (Zoll & Ackermann, 2001). Citizen participation is equally significant, with residents represented by local community members showing greater support for projects (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Corscadden et al., 2012; Langer et al., 2017; McLaren Loring, 2007; Upham & García Perez, 2015).

Having the four aforementioned factors (i)–(iv) in mind, we addressed the following research question (RQ1): **Do project ramifications also affect the attitudes of respondents who are negatively inclined towards the project in the region?** To answer this, we gathered quantitative data through semi-structured interviews, assessing whether elements such as smaller turbine designs or financial compensation schemes influence local attitudes positively or negatively. By examining a variety of factors within one survey, this report provides a holistic review of their impact on local attitudes across different regions.

In a second step, we integrate these findings with respondents' general attitudes toward wind energy and their views on projects in their region. Research indicates that community benefits and financial participation schemes can positively influence local acceptance, particularly among residents already favourably inclined toward wind energy (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Building on this assumption, we explore a second research question (RQ2): **Do certain project ramifications primarily affect the attitudes of respondents who are already positively inclined toward a project?** This question directly follows from RQ1.

To analyse respondents' attitudes, we structured the questionnaire into three parts addressing their general attitude towards wind energy (Part I), their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, regardless of specific project characteristics (Part II), and their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, with defined project characteristics (Part III). This approach follows Walter (2014), who differentiates between public attitude toward wind energy (general perceptions at the national level), attitude toward local wind energy projects (views on projects in one's vicinity irrespective of specific features), and local acceptance of wind energy projects (opinions on a specific project, considering its characteristics). A complete list of the questions posed in

Parts I–III is provided in Annex I, with additional details on the design process available in WIMBY Deliverable 4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024). Figure 11 provides a visualisation of the methodology.

Figure 11: Overview of methodological approach (Elaboration: Monika Bucha)

2.8 Other Activities

The first round of workshops in Viana do Castelo envisioned additional stakeholder engagement activities, planned to collect qualitative feedback on the Interactive map, the general forum and further insights about the overall project approach and methodology. Such activities were organised as follows:

- A short Interactive presentation of the WIMBY Interactive Map and General Forum including a real-time simulation
- Semi-structured interviews to selected stakeholders

The presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and the forum was provided to workshop participants by NAZKA: the presentation took overall 10 minutes, and it included a real-time simulation followed by a round of direct interaction with attendants. At the end of the simulation, participants provide informal feedback. In Section 3.5 the feedback collected is summarised and main takeaways highlighted.

Semi-structured recorded video interviews with selected stakeholders were collected with a two-fold ambition: i) collecting opinions and views related with wind-power energy and the local context that could feed results of quantitative surveys with qualitative insights ii) ensuring local voices would be heard and published at the local level, leveraging participation and opinion exchanges across the local community. To maximise visibility, when published, all links to video interviews have been shared with the belonging organisations and interviewees and of course published and promoted through all WIMBY public communication channels, after explicit consent.

To run interviews the Deep Blue team

- prepared a standard list of guiding questions (see Annex II), common to all pilot sites. (The questions were designed to guide the conversation and ensure key themes were addressed. However, the interviews remained flexible: depending on the background of the interviewee, their specific role or expertise, and the dynamics of the workshop, questions were adapted or reformulated on the spot to capture the most relevant insights and perspectives.)
- identified potential candidates in advance by liaising with pilot site leaders.
- collected signed consent forms from interviewees, authorising both the recording and the publication of the videos on WIMBY communication channels.
- planned 20-minute video-recording sessions.

Thanks to the informal setting and the set of open questions, interviewees were given time and opportunity to freely express their views and opinions. As a result, the team was able to capture the local nuances and perceptions of wind-energy projects and renewable energy systems at large. After recording, a preliminary version of edited interviews was sent to participants and pilot sites leader for approval before publication. In Section 3.5 highlights and key takeaways from interviews are summarised.

Additionally, APREN developed initiatives to communicate the project locally, creating content to bring awareness:

- Multimedia coverage of both workshops: APREN documented both workshops done in Portugal:
 - **Photo** coverage available upon request
 - **Video** coverage available on APREN's YouTube: <https://youtu.be/CaZmSzQpriQ>
- Media:
 - APREN sent a **press release** to the media, communicating the projects, its goals and the workshops done in the country (in Portuguese: <https://www.apren.pt/contents/communicationpressrelease/pr-apren--wimby-em-portugal.pdf> and in English <https://www.apren.pt/contents/communicationpressrelease/2025-02-05-pr-apren--wimby-in-portugal.pdf>)
 - Susana Serôdio (APREN's Head of Policy and Market Intelligence) wrote an **opinion article** where she mentioned the project (<https://www.renovaveismagazine.pt/engenharia-para-a-transicao-energetica/>)
- Social media posts: APREN promoted the project and its workshops through its social media platforms (see Figure 12 below: some examples from LinkedIn)

Figure 12: Social media posts APREN

3 Results and Discussion

Between 23 January and 31 January 2025, seven workshops were held at two different locations in Portugal. Three workshops took place in Viana do Castelo, a port city in northern Portugal, and four workshops in Torres Vedras, a city 50 kilometres north of Lisbon. A total of 53 people, mainly stakeholders, took part in the workshops. No workshops were held with pupils in Portugal.

3.1 Immersive 3D Planning Game

This chapter presents the results of the two game phases, the analysis of the baseline survey and the workshop evaluation.

3.1.1 Game phase 1: Go and No-go zones for Windfarm development

Pilot Site Viana do Castelo

In Viana do Castelo, three workshops were conducted, each following the same two-phase structure of the WIMBY participatory exercise. The first phase focused on identifying Go and No-Go zones for wind energy

development, aiming to understand how participants perceive spatial opportunities and constraints in the region. The exercise encouraged open discussion on where wind turbines could or should not be installed, based solely on local knowledge, landscape familiarity, and individual perceptions, without technical or project-specific framing.

Across all workshops, participants showed a clear convergence in identifying Go zones in industrial areas, open rural landscapes, and locations already influenced by human activity (see Figure 12). These were often described as less sensitive from a social and environmental perspective, with participants noting that such areas could accommodate additional wind turbines with limited perceived conflict.

Conversely, No-Go zones were consistently marked around villages, tourist zones, and environmentally protected or scenic areas, such as Natura 2000 sites, coastal landscapes, and popular hiking routes (see Figure 12). Participants expressed a general preference for avoiding visually prominent or densely populated locations, emphasising the importance of preserving the region's natural and cultural landscape values.

Overall, the mapping exercise revealed a strong alignment among participants regarding the balance between development potential and environmental or social constraints in Viana do Castelo. The activity also demonstrated the value of the 3D tool in supporting spatial reasoning and constructive dialogue on suitable and unsuitable areas for future wind energy projects.

Figure 13: Distribution and density of Go and No-Go zones in Viana do Castelo (Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Município, S.A.); Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Pilot Site Torres Vedras

The four sessions held in Torres Vedras began with a first phase focused on identifying Go and No-Go zones for wind energy development. Participants were invited to discuss, based on their local knowledge and familiarity with the territory, which areas appeared more or less suitable for wind deployment, without considering technical or regulatory aspects.

Across all sessions, participants generally marked Go zones (Figure 13) in areas already occupied by wind farms, as well as in open rural and inland landscapes with favourable wind conditions and limited population density. These locations were perceived as less sensitive to additional development and more compatible with the municipality's existing land use patterns. Some participants also pointed to elevated inland areas as potentially suitable, noting their distance from coastal and urban zones.

No-Go zones (Figure 13) were consistently placed around urban centres, coastal stretches, and areas of environmental or cultural importance. The coastal landscape was considered particularly valuable for its scenic, ecological, and recreational functions, while urban and residential areas were excluded due to their visual exposure and potential for social opposition. Several participants referred to the strong identity of Torres Vedras as a coastal and agricultural region, arguing that new turbines should avoid locations that could compromise that character.

Overall, the results for Torres Vedras showed a shared perception among participants of where wind energy development could be more acceptable and where it would likely face stronger constraints, highlighting the municipality's dual identity as both a productive inland territory and a sensitive coastal landscape.

Figure 14: Distribution and density of Go and No-Go zones in Torres Vedras (Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Municípa, S.A.); Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

3.1.2 Game phase 2: Virtual Windfarm development

The aim of game phase 2 was to develop repowering scenarios based on the previously identified Go zones. By removing existing turbines and placing modern and powerful wind turbines on the interactive game board, the effects on the landscape can be experienced in real time in the 3D environment. In addition, the contribution of the wind turbines to the game objectives explained in Section 1.2 (based on turbine sizes and local wind conditions) can be seen on the game board. With the help of VR glasses, immersive visualizations are also possible to better perceive realistic

perspectives and proportions. Below, two different repowering scenarios that were developed during the workshops are explained using fact sheets.

Repowering example “Viana do Castelo”

The repowering example in Viana do Castelo (see Figure 15) focused on the removal of 16 turbines with 2–3 MW capacity. The replacement with 7 new 6 MW turbines increased the total output from 322 GWh/a to 421 GWh/a which corresponds to an increase of approximately 30%. By reducing the number of turbines, the wind farm appears calmer and more structured from mid-range vistas (3–5 km) (viewpoint 1). At closer locations an increase in the impact on the landscape can be expected (viewpoint 2).

In addition to the larger dimensions, the option of blackening one rotor blade was also chosen in order to potentially reduce bird mortality (viewpoint 2 and 3). However, this was perceived as more unsettling and disruptive. Furthermore, experts in the workshop group believed that the wear and tear on the rotor blade caused by the intense sunlight in Portugal should not be underestimated. As a compromise, red stripes could be envisaged, which would primarily be used for flight safety but could also reduce bird mortality.

Viana do Castelo

Repowering in Viana do Castelo

SQ (Status Quo)

16 turbines
Capacity: 2-3 MW

RP (Repowering)

7 turbines
Capacity: 6 MW

Figure 15: Factsheet Repowering example: “Viana do Castelo” Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Município, S.A.), WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner

Repowering Example: “South of Torres Vedras”

A windfarm installed approx. 20 years ago that was in the visibility range of Torres Vedras is one example that was in scope for repowering (see Figure 16). In total, 19 turbines ranging from 0.6 to 2 MW capacity were removed to establish a new wind farm using 10 turbines with 6 MW capacity each. Although the number of turbines has been almost halved, the total output at this location has increased by 25% due to the larger and more powerful turbines. However, it is also apparent that the turbines appear much more prominent and closer, particularly from surrounding villages, due to their size (viewpoint 1 and viewpoint 2). This is important as this region was marked controversial due to the good visibility from the city of Torres Vedras.

Torres Vedras

Repowering in the South of Torres Vedras

SQ (Status Quo)

19 turbines
Capacity: 0,6-2 MW

RP (Repowering)

10 turbines
Capacity: 6 MW

Figure 16: Factsheet Repowering example: “South of Torres Vedras” Source: Open Street Map, IUCN and UNEP–WCMC, APREN (based on the DTM and DSM provided by Município, S.A.), WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

3.1.3 Analysis of questionnaires

The collected questionnaires were entered into an Excel spreadsheet and analysed using SPSS. This section summarises the results of the baseline survey of adults, the baseline survey of pupils and the results of the debrief questionnaires completed by both groups.

Baseline Survey Adults

The workshop participants in Portugal (n = 53) were 45 years old on average, with ages ranging from 26 to 76. Men accounted for 59.6% of the participants, while women accounted for 40.4%. All the respondents had a university or polytechnic degree, with 77.4% holding a bachelor's or master's degree and 22.6% holding a doctorate. Almost all working participants (96.2%) were in full-time employment, while 1.9% were retired. Many participants (64%) lived in a city. In Viana do Castelo (n = 24), half of the participants were from the region, whereas in Torres Vedras (n = 29), 82.1% were not, with 66.7% citing work as the reason. Additionally, 96.2% of all participants had professional experience in the field of renewable energy, with more than half (52%) had been working in their field for more than 10 years. The participants most frequently used the internet and social media (84.6%) as sources of information on renewable energies, followed by TV, radio and newspapers (53.8%) and academic journals (51.9%).

Most respondents in Portugal (88.7%) support the expansion of wind energy (see Figure 17a), with 35.8 % favouring preferential treatment for this form of energy. 86.5% of workshop participants believe wind energy can effectively contribute to the region's sustainable energy supply goals, and 51.9% believe it can meet energy needs effectively (see Figure 17c). However, 25% of respondents do not feel involved in decision-making processes regarding wind energy projects in their region (see Figure 17b). Interest in participating in activities to support wind energy initiatives is high, with 84.9% of respondents expressing interest, and 74% having already been involved in wind energy projects (see Figure 18a). Only 17.3% of respondents express concerns about wind energy projects in their region, while over a third actively campaigns for wind energy. 44.2% of those surveyed assess the potential environmental impacts of wind power, particularly regarding biodiversity and landscape aesthetics, as low (see Figure 18b). Nevertheless,

83% believe it is very important to conduct environmental impact assessments and implement mitigation measures for wind energy projects (see Figure 18c). Just 17.6% of respondents considered the incentives and opportunities for expanding wind energy to be high.

Figure 17: a) Do you generally support the expansion of wind energy? (n=53) b) Do you feel involved in the decision-making processes related to wind energy projects in your region? (n=52) c) In your opinion, how effectively could wind energy meet the energy demand in your region? (n=52)

In Portugal, 58.5% of workshop participants consider the involvement of various interest groups, such as associations and citizens' initiatives, to be very important for the success of wind energy projects. Furthermore, 60.4% of them expressed a willingness to participate in such groups to address implementation challenges. Respondents cited simplified approval procedures, incentives for investment in renewable energies, and urban planning regulations as the most important political measures for promoting wind energy projects. Public support for wind energy projects was rated as moderate by 41.5% of respondents (see Figure 18d), while 24.5% did not express an opinion. Social acceptance is also rated as moderate by the majority (60.4%).

Figure 18: a) Have you been involved in a wind energy project in the past? (n=50) b) How do you assess the potential environmental impacts of wind power, particularly regarding biodiversity and landscape aesthetics? (n=52) c) How important is it to conduct environmental impact assessments and implement mitigation measures for wind energy projects? (n=53) d) How do you rate the level of public support for wind energy projects in your community? (n=53)

Respondents see the greatest advantage of wind energy projects in the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, although the preservation of habitats is also important to them. They also believe that the local population should be involved in decision-making processes regarding location issues and the risks and benefits of such projects. In addition to regulatory challenges, they see grid integration as a challenge. For the respondents, the motivation to switch to regionally generated renewable energy lies primarily in the social, ecological and economic advantages, in particular lower energy costs and socio-economic benefits. When it comes to repowering wind turbines, 63.5% believe that this has a lower environmental impact than new construction (see Figure 19a), and 53.9% see it as an efficient way to contribute to the energy transition (see Figure 19b). In addition, over a third of respondents agreed with the statement that fewer but larger wind turbines may reduce the impact on the landscape (see Figure 19c) and almost a third agreed that distances from residential buildings should be introduced due to the size of such turbines. Over 50% hold a neutral stance on the statement that new wind turbines have a greater impact birds and bats due to their size (see Figure 19d).

Figure 19: Expected effects from repowering a) Repowering has a lower environmental impact than the construction new wind farms (n=52) b) Repowering is an efficient way to contribute to the energy transition (n=52) c) Fewer large wind turbines may reduce the landscape impact (n=52) d) Due to their size, the new turbines have a greater negative impact on birds and bats (n=51).

Baseline Survey Students

There were no workshops held with pupils in Portugal.

Workshop Feedback

37.7% of workshop participants stated that they had experience with video games, while 41.5% were only familiar with video games to a certain extent. Over 70% of respondents had previously played an educational game (77.4%) and used VR glasses (73.6%), even if only rarely.

Furthermore, 67.9% of the participants said that their overall experience of playing a wind energy game was positive (see Figure 20a), and 49.1% found the gaming experience engaging. More than half of the workshop participants felt that the objectives of the wind energy game were clearly communicated and that the game and its instructions were clear and easy to understand, besides there were opportunities for feedback. Additionally, over 50% of respondents found the game visually appealing and the interactive exercises and group discussions exciting and informative. 62.3%

stated that the workshop moderator guided the discussions and activities effectively.

Figure 20: Feedback a) Overall, the experience of participating in a wind energy game was positive (n=53) b) Did the workshop influence your perceptions or attitudes towards renewable energy? (n=53) c) Did the workshop meet your expectations addressing local key challenges and opportunities in wind energy projects? (n=53)

As these were expert workshops, it is unsurprising that 49.1% of respondents said that the workshop did not influence their perceptions or attitudes towards renewable energy (see Figure 20b). However, almost 40% of respondents said that the workshop increased their confidence in supporting wind energy initiatives. More than half of the workshop participants stated that the workshop had met their expectations regarding the local challenges and opportunities encountered in wind energy projects (see Figure 20c), and providing interesting insights from experts in the field. Most respondents (75.5%) said that group discussions fostered knowledge exchange and mutual learning.

Over 80% of those surveyed want to see more renewable energy initiatives and opportunities for community involvement and would like to participate in similar workshops or events in the future. Furthermore, 92.3% believe that the simulation game could be used to engage the local population in other regional topics, such as other renewable energy, industry and infrastructure projects.

3.2 MUSA

This section summarises preliminary results from the Portuguese pilot sites; a full technical analysis appears in Deliverable D4.6 (in progress). All pilot sites employed the same set of evaluation criteria: three overarching dimensions: environmental, community, and individual. They are subdivided into 12 specific sub-criteria (see Table 2). Each sub-criterion was measured on a scale suited to its nature: for instance, “Undesired land-use changes” used a four-point Likert scale, whereas “Reduction of greenhouse-gas emissions” was assessed on a five-point scale.

Table 2: Set of satisfaction criteria

Dimension (Criterion)	Sub-criterion
Environmental	Undesired land use changes
	Impact on biodiversity
	Reduce Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG)
Community	Economic impact on the community
	Negative effect on community lifestyle
	Safety risks to people and infrastructures
	Raise social awareness and political engagement
	Long term maintenance and decommissioning plans
Individual	Impact on personal finances
	Negative effect on the landscape’s aesthetics
	Disturbance from noise pollution
	Disturbance from shadow flicker

In Portugal, 83 residents completed the MCSA survey. Figure 21 shows the resulting satisfaction curves for each sub-criterion.

Figure 21: Sub-criteria satisfaction functions of Portugal responses

Satisfaction functions map respondents’ verbal assessments (e.g., “moderately satisfied”) to quantitative scores on a 0–100 scale using piecewise-linear curves. This mapping converts ordinal survey responses into cardinal values, enabling meaningful comparison and aggregation across criteria and groups. The specific shape of such mapping subcriteria satisfaction functions is obtained by solving an optimization problem fed with participant responses, with the notional objective to preserve the actual overall satisfaction of the respondents and avoid distortion effects; further details are found in D4.1-D4.3. Every curve begins at a satisfaction value of 0 for the lowest response level and rises to 100 at the highest, allowing us to read exactly how much satisfaction a given response implies. Take the sub-criterion “Undesired land-use changes,” posed as: “Do you believe that the construction of wind turbines will lead to undesirable land-use changes?” Respondents chose from four options: “To a large extent” (level 1), “To a

moderate extent" (level 2), "To a lesser extent" (level 3), and "Not at all" (level 4). If someone selects "To a lesser extent" (level 3), the curve assigns that response a satisfaction score of 97.92, indicating a very high level of comfort with the potential land-use impact, even it is not the highest level of satisfaction on this criterion. The shape of each satisfaction curve also reveals how demanding participants are. For the sub-criterion "Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emission," the curve rises slowly at the second response level, satisfaction reaches only 14.1, well below the neutral benchmark of 25 on a five-point scale. This indicates residents who answer this question on the first and second levels set a high bar for emissions performance. However, because satisfaction jumps sharply at higher response levels (surpassing neutrality by the third level), the overall demanding index for this criterion remains low. In contrast, all other sub-criteria show steeper initial slopes, confirming that participants are generally non-demanding on those issues. Note that the MUSA questionnaire elicits status-quo satisfaction with the wind farm. Because this framing targets perceived satisfaction rather than stated choices or willingness to trade off, MUSA outputs may differ from results produced by other models that use different question formats or behavioural assumptions.

3.3 Mental Models

In the Portuguese case study sites, participants (N = 48) incorporated an average of 11.31 distinct concepts (SD = 3.56) into their mental models, connected by an average of 12.48 arrows (SD = 5.64). The most frequently included impacts were CO₂ Reduction, Sustainable Energy, and Noise Emissions. Accordingly, the most commonly used direct connection was between Wind Farm and Sustainable Energy, followed by links to Noise Emissions and Visual Landscape Change. Participants demonstrated a strong awareness of the causal chain linking Sustainable Energy, CO₂ Reduction, and Climate Change. The most frequently represented indirect connections were from CO₂ Reduction to Climate Change, and from Sustainable Energy to CO₂ Reduction. Additionally, Animal Fatalities and Wildlife Disruption were often linked to Biodiversity Loss. Support for wind energy among the Portuguese participants was notably high, with a mean score of 87.52 (SD = 12.68). This elevated support level is likely influenced by

the sample’s composition, which consisted predominantly of pro-wind stakeholders. Overall, the participants represented a balanced range of impacts, though social impacts were less frequently included (see Figure 22). A notable emphasis was placed on impacts such as Noise Emissions and Visual Landscape Change, which may reflect the relatively less restrictive distance regulations for wind farm siting in Portugal compared to the other case study regions.

Figure 22: Aggregated mental model of wind farm impacts among participants from Portugal. The thickness of the arrows represents the total weight of the connections across individual mental models, with thicker arrows indicating stronger connections. Note: Only connections with an above-average aggregated weight are shown (Source: Mental model data, Graphic: Leanda Vedder)

3.4 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

In total, 22 interview (27% female, 73% male) were conducted in Torres Vedras, both during the project workshops (see Section 2.3) and in public spaces such as streets, churches, and municipal buildings. Some participants were contacted in advance via email and via phone to arrange a meeting, and interviews lasted between 15 - 60 minutes.

These interviews provided a small snapshot of local attitudes toward wind energy projects. Based on question (in the following: Q) 1–8 (see Section 6.1), two respondent opposed wind energy, eight were neutral, and twelve were supportive (see Figure 23a). When asked directly about their feelings toward the construction of a hypothetical wind energy project in their vicinity (Q11), no respondent expressed negative or very negative feelings, while nine expressed neutral feelings (see pie to the left in Figure 23b). The majority of them considered project participation to not be important (at all) (Q12; see Figure 23b, right pie). This suggests that this part of respondents will hardly be convinced when offered certain project ramifications. This hypothesis will be examined further in the following paragraphs.

Figure 23: a) General attitude towards wind energy (n = 22) b) Feelings towards wind energy projects & the importance to participate (n = 22)

The analysis of **question 13** (*Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?*) revealed that seven respondents supported changes to setback distances, six supported altering turbine heights, five supported altering the number of turbines and two supported technical measures to avoid bird strikes (see Figure 24, left pies). In other words, our study shows that about 9–32% of respondents indicated increased support when technical adaptations addressed either (i) environmental impacts or (ii) the physical characteristics of wind energy projects.

Between 14–50% of respondents who indicated increased support when technical adaptations were offered in Q11 reported neutral attitudes towards

wind energy projects in their region. This suggests that while some measures primarily strengthen support among those already convinced, certain adaptations can also influence neutral respondents. Among the four technical measures in Q13, preventing bird strikes was the most effective, with 50% of neutral or negative respondents indicating increased acceptance, followed by reducing the number of turbines (20%), modifying setback distances (17%) and adjusting turbine height (14%) (see Figure 24, right pies).

Figure 24: Technical changes which would increase one’s willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 22)

Question 14 (Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?) showed that financial participation was particularly appealing: 19 respondents supported discounted electricity, 8 supported financial participation for their municipality, 5 preferred acquiring shares with personal funds, and 4 supported acquiring shares through external financing (see Figure 25, left pies). In total, 18–86% of respondents were more willing to support a project when offered financial participation schemes which directly address (iii) the distribution of ills and benefits.

Between 20–47% of respondents who indicated increased support when technical adaptations were offered in Q11 reported neutral attitudes towards wind energy projects in their region. Again, while some mechanisms appeal mainly to supporters, others influence neutral respondents. Being offered discounted electricity proved most effective (47%), followed by financial participation of the municipality (38%), having the possibility to acquire project shares with foreign money (25%), and having the possibility to acquire shares in the project with own money (20%) (see Figure 25, right pies).

The fact that a large number of respondents were convinced by discounted electricity prices also reflects the conversations we had during the semi-structured interviews. Several interviewees said they were promised cheaper electricity prices and were disappointed that they did not notice them in their monthly energy bills.

Figure 25: Financial participation mechanisms which would increase one’s willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 22)

For **question 15** (Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support

wind energy projects in your region?), eight respondents supported early involvement, another eight preferred regular written updates, five favoured involvement in project implementation and one having a municipal representative on the board of directors (see Figure 26, left pies). Overall, 5–36% of respondents showed increased willingness to support a project when given opportunities for active engagement in decision-making, indirectly depending on (iv) the behaviour of wind energy project developers. Between 13–50% of respondents who indicated increased support when technical adaptations were offered in Q11 reported neutral attitudes towards wind energy projects in their region. Among the measures, regular written updates (50%) were most effective, followed by early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (13%) (see Figure 26, right pies).

Figure 26: Options for engagement in the decision-making processes which would increase one's willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 22)

The measures most effective at convincing respondents with neutral attitudes (Q11) were: discounted electricity (100% of respondents with neutral attitudes indicated the measures were apt to increase their willingness to support the wind energy project), regular written updates (44%), financial

participation of the municipality (33%), change in setback distance, technical measures to avoid bird strikes, change in the number of turbines, change in turbine height, possibility to acquire project shares with own money and with foreign money, and early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (each 11%).

It should be noted that no interviews were conducted in Viana de Castelo.

3.5 Other Activities

Interactive map and General Forum interactive session

Shortly before the 3D workshop started, participants gathered in a plenary session where the NAZKA team presented the WIMBY Interactive map and general forum. Such session aimed at showcasing the potentiality and different uses of the platform to the participants and collect their feedback on-the-spot. Due to the limited time availability, most of the time was dedicated to answering questions related to its features and underlined its user-friendliness. Some participants asked questions about how the co-creation process took place and who was involved in them. After the presentation participants moved to another part of the room where the 3D workshop was about to begin. Partners NAZKA, DEEP BLUE, UU and BOKU agreed that presenting the interactive map and general forum before the 3D workshop was beneficial, since it allowed a faster engagement and comprehension of the upcoming “wind-farm planning” tasks in the VR environment. This was not the case in some previous workshops in Pantelleria, where the Interactive map presentations took place afterwards. No further takeaways emerged from the workshop in Torres Vedras. Unfortunately, it was not possible to present the map in Viana do Castelo on the next day, due to very limited time and logistic barriers.

Video Interviews

Overall, for the Portuguese case five video interviews were made. Four of them in Viana Do Castelo, plus an additional interview to partner APREN recorded previously during the General Assembly Meeting in Vienna.

All interviews can be found on the WIMBY YouTube playlist³. Key messages are summarised in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Summary of stakeholder interviews

Susana Serôdio	PS Leader at APREN	Wind is around 30% of the electricity generated in Portugal, but repowering is now needed since many turbines are approaching repowering. It is essential to understand clearly what new barriers and criteria shall be considered in order to guide this process.
Ana Carreto	Sustainability leader at ENDESA	New technologies such as that developed by WIMBY could really help improve communication across citizens and local authorities. Questions often arise around localisation and concerns shall be properly addressed. Also, such tools can help better understand the opportunities, if we learn how to enhance knowledge exchange.
Sofia Soares	Geologist at the National Laboratory for Energy and Geology	The model could be improved, geological layers could be added to better understand not only biodiversity better but also noise impact. The limestone for example has many cavities and foundations to support their weight might be bigger compared to other types of soil. We shall reconcile also these aspects, where do concrete foundations go when the turbine is dismantled? People are not so aware of it, it could help improve evaluations. In the end we shall minimise impacts, and thanks to open data we can share more information and better manage things, take more accurate decisions.
Filipe Moreira Alves	Researcher at the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon	The tools developed in the project, like 3D visualisation and impact assessment maps, can really help local communities better understand potential future impacts of wind farms in regions such as Torres Vedras. Combining technical tools with socio-economic and governance considerations is essential to ensure inclusive energy transitions.

3

<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLna5U7-OPgOtnOyUQbQhSDyjtFc8yE--p&si=vED0egy6ddPw1Va3>

<p>Alcino Antunes</p>	<p>Electrical engineer</p>	<p>It's much easier to understand how a wind farm impacts the community thanks to such tools, since you are able to really see their proximity to houses and better evaluate different factors. This really helps shape the perception, have a closer notion of the reality and hopefully better accept it. Maybe it is not that interesting for the general public, but it can help a lot the designers, planners and those in charge of evaluating the links with the distribution network too.</p>
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Figure 27: Video snapshots from the interviews

4 Conclusion and recommendations

The Portuguese pilot within the WIMBY project provided valuable insights into how participatory and analytical tools can jointly contribute to a more transparent, informed, and socially grounded approach to wind energy planning. Through a combination of interactive workshops, quantitative satisfaction analysis, and semi-structured interviews, the study captured both spatial and perceptual dimensions of public acceptance. The results underline that while Portugal's wind sector is mature, the next phase of development, particularly repowering, will depend increasingly on how projects are perceived and discussed at a local level. The activities in Viana do Castelo and Torres Vedras demonstrated that meaningful engagement, clear communication of the visual impact, and accessibility of information are essential to building trust among communities and to supporting well-informed permitting processes.

The interactive 3D tool proved to be a highly relevant instrument for exploring key considerations for the permitting of wind energy projects in a simulated context. It enabled authorities and other stakeholders to better understand the spatial and visual characteristics of hypothetical developments and to discuss their potential implications in a realistic yet controlled environment. By providing an immersive visualisation of turbine placement within the surrounding landscape, the tool helped participants engage more effectively with complex spatial information and facilitated more grounded discussions on site suitability and perception.

It also served as an effective means of assessing the visual impact of repowering projects, particularly in cases where the number of turbines is reduced while their height and capacity increase. The visual simulations prompted interesting reflections among participants, many of whom expressed a preference for layouts with a greater number of smaller turbines (around 4 MW) rather than fewer, larger ones (6 MW), especially in areas close to residential zones.

Looking ahead, the integration of additional data layers, particularly information on available grid infrastructure, could be valuable. Furthermore, given that most of projects in Portugal are considering early-stage hybridisation, scaling the tools to other forms of renewable energy could further enhance their usefulness, making them a valuable resource for project planning, spatial optimisation and early stakeholder engagement in Portugal.

In parallel, the application of the MUSA framework indicated that participants were generally tolerant towards most local impacts of wind projects, showing very high satisfaction scores for issues such as land-use changes. In contrast, they proved more demanding regarding greenhouse gas reduction, setting a higher threshold before considering this criterion satisfactorily met. Overall, the results suggest that social acceptance depends more on perceived environmental performance than on local land-use concerns. The combination of this approach with the participatory mapping delivered a more comprehensive understanding of social acceptance dynamics, showing that community attitudes depend not only

on spatial location but also on the perceived balance between visual, ecological and socio-economic dimensions.

The semi-structured interviews 3.4 indicate that certain project ramifications can significantly influence local attitudes towards a wind energy project, including among those initially opposed. The measures most effective in convincing respondents with negative views were offering discounted electricity, regular written updates, and financial participation of the municipality.

While our study offers only a snapshot of local attitudes within a relatively small population, and broad generalisations should therefore be avoided, the findings do suggest that employing a wide range of participation methods increases the likelihood of engaging a broader spectrum of residents. Policymakers are therefore advised to adopt a diverse set of methods – including early consultation, the use of VR simulations, and financial participation schemes – to strengthen local trust and enhance project acceptance.

Overall, these complementary methods demonstrate the value of combining participatory and analytical tools to strengthen mutual understanding between developers, authorities, and local communities. By making spatial and perceptual information more tangible and transparent, the WIMBY approach supports a more inclusive and evidence-based planning process for wind energy development and repowering in Portugal.

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6 ANNEX

6.1 Annex I: Semi-structured interview conducted to assess the impact of project ramifications on respondent's concrete attitude towards wind energy projects

Table 4: Semi-structured interview

	Question	Answer	
PART I General attitude towards wind energy	1_Do you believe climate change is human-induced and that it is one of the biggest problems of our times?	1 (strongly disagree) 2 (disagree) 3 (neutral) 4 (agree) 5 (strongly agree)	
	2_ Regarding the environment do you agree that the protection of global biodiversity may require to accept worse conditions for local species?		
	3_Do you believe that our actions at the local level can make a difference to solving global problems?		
	4_Do you agree that everyone in your local society has a common responsibility to care for each other in challenging times?		
	5_When faced with a project challenge, do you prioritize finding the most effective solution regardless of cost?		
	6_When new technological innovations are introduced, do you think that debt should be taken on (with the associated risk) to explore and implement them?		
	7_Do feel that the problems relating to solving climate change issues are of too complex and that we lack the resources (time, training, etc.) to understand them?		
	8_Do you believe that radical changes, incl. technological advancements, (as opposed to traditional methods) are necessary to preserve our habitat and wellbeing?		
PART II Concrete attitude towards wind energy	9_How much do you know about Energy Transition in general?	1 (not informed at all) 2 (not well informed) 3 (moderately) 4 (well informed) 5 (very well informed)	
	10_Do you feel well-informed about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (not at all) 2 (slightly) 3 (moderately) 4 (well) 5 (very well)	
	11_How do you feel about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (very negative) 2 (negative) 3 (neutral) 4 (positive) 5 (very positive)	
	12_How important do you see your participation in the wind project?	1 (not important at all) 2 (not important) 3 (neutral) 4 (important) 5 (very important)	
PART III project ramifications	13_Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_change in setback distance	(i)
		B_technical measures to avoid bird strikes	
		C_change in turbine height	(ii)
		D_change in number of wind turbines	
	14_Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_discounted electricity / lower energy prices	(iii)
B_possibility to acquire shares in the project with own money (dividends / appreciation of shares)			
C_possibility to acquire shares in the project with credit from project (dividends / appreciation of shares)			
	D_financial participation of the municipality		
	A_regular written information on the project progress	(iv)	

15_Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	B_early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (once per month / quarterly)	
	C_involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction (once per month / quarterly)	
	D_being granted elected representative of the municipality on the board of directors of the project (actual operation of wind park)	

6.2 Annex II: Guiding questions for interviews with workshop participants

1. **General perception** – What is your personal opinion on wind energy in general and its development in Europe?
2. **Local context** – How do you think wind energy could impact your community or region?
3. **Opportunities** – What benefits or opportunities do you see in the development of wind farms locally?
4. **Concerns** – Are there any aspects that worry you or that you think should be addressed more carefully (e.g. landscape, noise, biodiversity, tourism, health)?
5. **Social acceptance** – In your view, what factors could increase or decrease public acceptance of wind energy projects?
6. **Stakeholder involvement** – How do you think citizens and stakeholders should be involved in the decision-making processes?
7. **Support tools** – How useful do you find tools such as interactive maps or online forums to facilitate participation and understanding of projects?
8. **Fairness & benefits** – Do you think measures like financial compensation or community participation schemes could help build greater support?
9. **Personal experiences** – Have you had any direct or indirect experiences with wind projects? If yes, what worked well and what didn't?
10. **Future vision** – What role do you see for wind energy (and renewables in general) in the energy transition of your territory?